

Automated curation of spatial metadata in environmental monitoring data

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ABSTRACT

Spatial data accuracy in environmental monitoring is crucial for practical large-scale data analytics and the development of AI models. In this context, spatial data is metadata and faces the same challenges as any other metadata, like missing values, false or contradicting information, formatting problems of textual data and numbers, the usage of different languages, and more. These issues severely limit the usability of the data.

With this study, we provide an automatic approach, CleanGeoStreamR, to resolve as many of these issues as possible for the spatially annotated environmental monitoring database. We substantially increased the quality of the spatial metadata and, therefore, the quantity of data points that can be used in large-scale data analytics and AI applications.

Further, our goal is to raise awareness about the issues related to spatial metadata and promote the implementation of our concepts in other environmental monitoring data sources. Advanced understanding and the availability of automatic approaches like the presented method will substantially contribute to making environmental monitoring data FAIR and enhance its usability in the era of Big Data and AI.

1. Introduction

Environmental monitoring involves observing and assessing an environment to measure the impact of disturbing activities on it and assess risks (Hamel et al., 2024). The main types of environmental monitoring are soil, atmosphere or air, and water. While our study focused on water, the proposed concepts are transferable to the other matrices.

Monitoring programs are coordinated among federal, state, and local agencies, universities, and volunteers. The National Water Quality Monitoring Council, coordinated by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) provides the Water Quality Portal (WQP) (National Quality Monitoring Council and U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2004), the country's most used water quality monitoring resource. The UN Global Environment Monitoring System for Freshwater (GEMS/Water) (U.N. GEMS/Water Global Programme Coordination Unit, 2024) provides sound data on freshwater quality for scientific assessments and decision-making. At the EU level, the Water Framework Directive (European Commission, 2015) defines rules to halt deterioration in Europe's rivers, lakes, and groundwater. The NORMAN network (Dulio and Slobodnik, 2009) is a network of reference laboratories, research centers, and related organizations that exchange information on emerging substances in Europe's environment. It encourages the validation and harmonization of measurement methods

and monitoring tools. It aims to provide FAIR data to fulfill the requirements of risk assessors and managers and directly cooperates with The Partnership for Chemicals Risk Assessment (PARC) (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023; Dulio et al., 2020).

The collection of geospatial information, including geographical location and natural features, alongside monitoring data has gained increasing importance in recent years, as it enables more precise analysis and understanding of environmental patterns and changes.

Geospatial data play a crucial role in understanding and managing our natural environment, for example, to identify vulnerable areas or sources of pollution that require action or further regulation. Further, such data can reveal suitable locations related to future land use or enhanced natural resource planning (Lacroix et al., 2019; Balasubramani, 2018). Predicting flood and drought events and consequently decreasing or increasing concentrations of pollutants in surface waters have become highly relevant applications of such data (Kao et al., 2020; Semenov et al., 2024) in the era of artificial intelligence.

Challenges and limitations of geo-spatially annotated environmental data include its quality and accuracy, privacy considerations, technical limitations, infrastructure requirements, and data integration and interoperability (Coetzee et al., 2020). Missing values and inconsistent

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information are frequent, e.g., due to different origins, formats, multiple processing steps, sensitive (masked) information about properties, or critical infrastructure, and insufficient technical capabilities (Hong et al., 2023; Tsatsaris et al., 2021) or various monitoring devices, experimental setups, and study scopes. During data collection, recording, and digitalization, the human factor also introduces errors like typos and transcription mistakes, which can lead to inaccuracies in recorded values. Manual data entry, especially when coordinates are involved, raises the risk of switching latitude and longitude or using different number formats, resulting in incorrect geospatial annotations.

Naturally, the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the spatial information of environmental monitoring data is key for any respective Big Data analytics and AI application (Xu and Zhang, 2023; Massarelli et al., 2023).

The Chemical Occurrence Database — EMPODAT is part of the NORMAN database system (NDS). It is the premier European source of geo-referenced and bio-monitoring data on emerging substances in water, sediments, biota, suspended particulate matter, soil, sewage sludge, and air matrices (Dulio et al., 2018). Our study focused on the spatial metadata annotation of sampling sites in the surface water tables of EMPODAT. The sampling location is identified by the sampling site's name, the river basin, water body, country, and coordinate information. Observed issues with this data include missing values, inconsistent number formats, and naming of sampling sites, countries, rivers, and water bodies, false data, and contradicting information. Partly, missing values exist on purpose due to a required masking step. However, these cases cannot be distinguished from unintentionally missing values. Textual data often originate from different languages and spelling variants and contain typos (Chua et al., 2018). Problems with numbers arise from different formats, the precision of decimal places, and the actual value of the coordinates to be valid longitude or latitude. Many errors are human-made (Ilyas and Naumann, 2022), which is natural in large-scale monitoring studies comprising the work of researchers from different institutions and projects with varying foci and rules on relevant, optional, and required metadata.

The NORMAN network has collected data over 20 years from hundreds of institutions and projects (Brack et al., 2012). They work hard to meet the enormous challenge of keeping that data consistent and valuable for the community, aiming at a FAIR data resource. The NDS provides formatted Excel sheets for metadata collection. The improvement of metadata collection in the future is discussed frequently in NORMAN committee meetings and within the PARC framework, where data scientists and NORMAN committee members come together. While these activities require time to consolidate among the research institutions, errors must be resolved for existing data.

Here, we present **CleanGeoStreamR**—an automatic curation pipeline for geo-spatially annotated data. Challenges and limitations of using such data in Big Data Science studies arise from human and technical errors. CleanGeoStreamR (i) identifies problems, (ii) assigns these to defined cases, (iii) ranks these by their complexity, importance for data analytics projects, and the number of affected data points, and (iv) resolves as many issues as possible without human interaction. Our goals are to provide (I) an automated pipeline that the maintainers of the NDS and data scientists working with the current EMPODAT data can use, (II) curated geospatial metadata for the millions of data points of the EMPODAT, and (III) increased awareness of occurring issues that limit the automatic processing of spatially annotated monitoring data. While we applied CleanGeoStreamR to one specific database system, CleanGeoStreamR is implemented as a flexible solution such that our concepts are adaptable to other spatially annotated monitoring data that face similar problems.

2. Materials and methods

The data was downloaded from the Norman Database System (<https://www.norman-network.com/nds/>), i.e., the Substance Database (susdat) and the Chemical Occurrence Database (empodat), both on April 24, 2024 as .csv files. In the Chemical Occurrence Database SEARCH option, we selected the Ecosystems/matrices *Surface water — River, Lake, and Transitional water, Reservoirs, and others*. We received 120 556 for susdat and 92 251 604 for empodat, respectively. We downloaded spatial data for rivers, lakes, oceans, countries, and continents from the *Physical and Cultural, Large scale data, 1:10m* section of the Natural Earth resource (<https://www.naturalearthdata.com/>). This (input) data, including header and column type information, was uploaded to Zenodo. Instructions on creating header and column type information for novel downloads or alternative datasets are provided in the CleanGeoStreamR GitLab repository; see Data Availability section. The R programming language (version 4.2.3, 2023-03-15) with the tidyverse (version 1.3.2) and the simple features (sf) package (version 1.0-12) were used to investigate the data and develop the R package. We refer to the CleanGeoStreamR GitLab repository for further information on package dependencies.

According to the **metadata standard for geographic information**, ISO 19115 (International Organization for Standardization, 2014), appropriate descriptive XML files for the key outputs are provided in the CleanGeoStreamR GitLab repository and Zenodo.

The **workflow** comprised four steps: (1) initialization, (2) pre-processing, (3) data curation, and (4) finalization; see Fig. 1. Each step operates on the entire dataset, incorporating all fixes from the previous steps.

In the *initialization* phase, CleanGeoStreamR loads the input data in step 1a and prepares the computational environment to ensure the availability of all packages in appropriate releases in step 1b.

In the *pre-processing* step 2, CleanGeoStreamR normalizes textual data of the sampling site, country, river, and water body names, focussing on used language, spelling, typos, and capitalization. In particular, CleanGeoStreamR uses the *stri_trans_general* function from the *stringi* R package for a Latin-ASCII transformation to normalize any language-specific characters, removes all punctuations and not required spaces. Subsequently, the tool transfers all text to lowercase. In this step, CleanGeoStreamR identifies a unique set of sampling sites based on the normalized textual data.

The *data curation* step 3 is CleanGeoStreamR's central part. The primary key to identifying a sampling site is its name. Based on this assumption, all other geospatial features are curated to keep and generate unique sampling site names. Similar problems were categorized into cases, with issues resolved at the level of individual sampling sites. This information was then transferred to all data points containing measurements for the respective sampling site. A brief description of these cases along with examples for each case is provided in Section 3, Table 2.

Step 3a resolves missing and inconsistent river and water body names for sampling sites with the same name. The sites were grouped by name, and those with missing river basin or water body names were dropped. If the river basin and water body names are consistent for the remaining entries of this site, they were used (case 1). If only one river basin or water body name was provided, the missing value is filled with the respective other (case 2). A majority vote is held in cases where the provided river basin and water body names are inconsistent. The most used values are accepted (case 3).

Step 3b fills in missing sampling site names via reverse geocoding using the provided river basin, water body names, and coordinates (case 4). Language variations of river basin and water body names were translated into English using a manually generated list (case 5).

Step 3c averages over minor deviations, a radius of 0.8 degrees of spatial coordinates for the same sampling site. Sites with the same name but

Fig. 1. Workflow of the sequential steps implemented in CleanGeoStreamR. Abbreviations: wbn — water body name, rbn — river basin name.

more diverging coordinates were considered separate sampling sites, and their coordinates were added to the name of the site (case 6). Step 3d decides on controversial sampling site–country and coordinates–country information. The provided coordinates and textual data are compared with the Natural Earth resources. The combination with the highest level of support is selected (case 7). Sampling sites of marine origin in the Natural Earth resources are tagged additionally.

Step 4a tags all touched entries from the input data with the deployed solutions (cases). Step 4b creates a log file containing the fixes and exports the curated data.

3. Results

The downloaded surface water data from EMPODAT comprised 92 251 604 *data points* holding chemical concentrations monitored at 30 165 *sampling sites* for multiple time points between 1998 and 2024. The spatial metadata of the sampling sites includes columns for country, sampling site, water body, and river basin names, as well as the geographical coordinates, in degrees-minutes-seconds (DMS) and decimal formats.

The quality of the input data significantly suffered from three main challenges: missing, inconsistent, and wrong data. The missing values are spread across all columns of the data, primarily over coordinates, water body, and river basin names, where the percentages of NA values ranged between 76 and 93 %. See [Table 1](#) for the actual numbers and percentages of missing values (*NAs*) from the perspective of unique sampling sites and total data points.

Inconsistencies in (a) textual metadata, particularly in the names of sampling sites, water bodies, and river basins, and (b) number formats for numerical data, particularly in the coordinate columns, were also evident. Various researchers have collected data from hundreds of laboratories over 20 or more years. The request for consistent metadata provision or more regulation has existed for a few recent years and is in the process of improvement. However, the ‘older’ data, collected in multiple languages with spelling variations, typographical errors, and inconsistencies in decimal separators, significantly affects the current state of the dataset. We observed false data for country coordinates and sampling site name-coordinate pairs or the association of one sampling site to different water bodies or river basins. To increase the integrity, uniformity, quality, and re-usability of the overall dataset, we developed the automatic workflow CleanGeoStreamR to normalize textual and numerical data comprehensively, fill missing data wherever possible, and correct wrong associations for all unique sampling sites.

Many combinations of values in the denoted columns do not fit together and must be resolved. When only a single column does not fit the information in the other columns, the correct value can be retrieved quickly using data provided for the same sampling site or geocoding methods. On the other hand, if multiple columns do not fit or incorrect combinations combine with missing values, it is more challenging to decide which information is the truth and suitable for resolving the incorrect information in the other columns. For example, two measurements at the same sampling site were given, and both were assigned to France. However, the coordinates pointed to Spain; the water body and river names were missing. In such situations, it is entirely unclear if the truth lies in the coordinates or the country associations.

To track our curations, we summarized the observed issues into cases. We refer to the Materials and Methods Section 2 for details on

Table 1

Numbers (*N*) and percentages (in %) of missing values (= data gaps) from the perspective of unique sampling sites and total data points. Note that different percentages of data points might be affected than sampling sites. Some sampling sites are investigated more often, so more data points are available.

Variable	Sampling sites		Data points	
	<i>N</i>	in %	<i>N</i>	in %
Water body name	20 407	67.60	85 936 061	93.20
River basin name	19 356	64.20	74 048 255	80.30
Coordinates	13 445	44.50	70 823 155	76.80
Site name	10	0.03	26 592	0.03

the algorithms and [Table 2](#) for examples of each case. Please note that in many cases, the observed problems are of multiple origins. For example, if the names of the water bodies and river basins are inconsistent or missing, often no coordinates are given. In the worst case, observed situations involve one, two, or all three issues—missing, inconsistent, and wrong data. We tagged each treated record with the case number or multiple case numbers if several treatments were deployed to improve it.

The largest effect on the data involved curating the variation of coordinates for the same sampling sites. Assigning average coordinates or adding the coordinate information to the sampling site names (case 6) resulted in adjustments for over 10 thousand sites and affected 37.6 million data points. We considered both the geographic context and the coordinate distribution to define a meaningful threshold *t* for the coordinates to join sampling sites. We decided on $t = 0.8^\circ$, which amounts to ~ 89 km for latitude and ~ 63 km for longitude. A smaller *t* would risk unnecessarily fragmenting these clusters, while a higher *t* might merge distinct sites (see [Fig. 2](#)).

The second significant effect on the data points was observed for inconsistencies in water body and river basin names (case 3); see [Table 2](#) for examples. Their corrections involved nearly 1.7 thousand sites and around 25.5 million data points. The unification of water body and river basin names in terms of language, abbreviations, and spelling variations (case 5) involved refining around 6 thousand sites and impacting 17.7 million data points. For sites where only partial information was missing, either water body or river basin (case 2), we augmented that information from other measurements at the same site for 3.1 thousand sites, affecting about 3.2 million data points. For 510 sampling sites, we successfully filled missing river and water body names (case 1), which affected approximately 511 thousand data points, see [Fig. 3 C](#). For more details regarding the exact number of modifications for all cases, please see [Table 3](#). Further, see [Fig. 3 A–B](#) for examples of wrong country associations considering the coordinates as the truth. [Fig. 3 E](#) shows the numbers and percentages of missing, inconsistent, or wrong values fixed with CleanGeoStreamR.

Geocoordinates were provided in degree-minute-second (DMS) and decimal format, though more than 40 % of the sites show missing values in one or both features. While for 77 sites, we could recover the missing decimal from the provided DMS coordinates. The input data provided none of the two variants for the remaining 13 445 sampling sites. We employed reverse geocoding to retrieve coordinates from a combination of the (curated) names of the sampling site, the water body, and river basin names. We successfully filled such data gaps for 2288 sampling sites. In addition, the dataset contained irrelevant marine sites ([Fig. 3 D](#)) and sites not located in European countries. Both should not be there due to our initial selections from the NORMAN

Table 2

Brief description of the considered cases in the automated data curation workflow of step 3. Sampling site names are in part abbreviated for a clearer presentation. Coordinates were rounded to their second digit. Red color indicates the problematic values, Blue the deployed solution. Dashed line indicates a new sampling site.

Case Number	Definition	water body name	river basin name	country	lat	lon
1	Fill missing river basin AND water body names for the same sites					
	lambrina	po	lambro	Italy	45.20	9.54
	lambrina	NA	NA	Italy	45.20	9.54
2	Fill missing river basin OR water body names for the same site					
	sarthe a arnage	loire bretagne	NA	France	47.90	0.14
	tp staumauer	NA	ts rauschenbach	Germany	50.70	13.5
3	Resolve inconsistent river basin AND/OR water body names for the same site					
	klcovsky potok	klcovsky potok	klcovsky potok	Slovakia	49.00	20.70
	klcovsky potok	NA	klcovsky potok	Slovakia	49.00	20.70
	klcovsky potok	klcovsky p	klcovsky p	Slovakia	49.00	20.70
	skovde wwtp us morkerriveren	se3	se3	France		
	skovde wwtp us morkerriveren	se3	NA	France	NA	NA
	skovde wwtp us morkerriveren	se4	se4	France		
4	Curate sampling site names with reverse geocoding					
	NA	le lunain a lorrezlebocageprRaux	seine	France	48.24	2.88
	lorrezlebocage fontainebleau	le lunain a lorrezlebocageprRaux	seine	France	48.24	2.88
5	Unify river basin and water body names regarding used language/variation					
	pod slovnaftom as bratislava	dunaj	dunaj	Slovakia	NA	NA
	pod slovnaftom as bratislava	danube	danube	Slovakia	NA	NA
	upstream wwtp w. regensdorf	furtbach	rhein	Switzerland	NA	NA
	upstream wwtp w. regensdorf	furtbach	rhine	Switzerland	NA	NA
6	Assign average coordinates or add coordinates to site name					
	bresso seveso po it	seveso	po	Italy	45.54	9.18
	bresso seveso po it	seveso	po	Italy	45.53	9.19
	bresso seveso po it	seveso	po	Italy	45.54	9.19
	bresso seveso po it	seveso	po	Italy	46.63	10.28
	.46.63,10.28					
7	Curate controversial sampling site and country pairs					
	ds tisaupstream sava belegis	danube	danube	Austria	45.00	20.37
	ds tisaupstream sava belegis	danube	danube	Serbia	45.00	20.37

Fig. 2. Example case for a site that has widely spread sample locations. A: Representation of the sample locations on the map, showing the spatial distribution. B: Samples that lie inside the threshold. C: Samples that exceed the defined threshold value.

website when downloading. Thus, we tagged the involved data points as *MARINE* or *non-EUROPEAN*, respectively.

In our analysis, we paid specific attention to the columns “country”, “station name”, “river body name”, “water basin name”, “latitude”, and “longitude”, which we deemed relatively important for the dataset’s overall integrity. Across these columns, there were a total of 301 644 449 missing values (NAs). We successfully filled 107 445 957 of these missing values, meaning ~ 36% of the total data gaps, see Fig. 3 F. This

is a substantial improvement that enhances the dataset’s overall integrity and reliability, making it a more robust resource for subsequent analyses.

We developed CleanGeoStreamR as an R package that automatically curates all fixable problems with geospatial metadata of monitoring measurements but may be applied to other experimental data where such metadata is involved. It is a flexible approach regarding the input data, selecting relevant textual columns and defined thresholds. CleanGeoStreamR is available under the GNU General Public License at

Table 3

Numbers (*N*) and percentages (in %) of curated data points stratified by their case number from the perspective of unique sampling sites and total data points. Note that different percentages of data points might be affected than sampling sites. Some sampling sites are investigated more often, so more data points are available.

Case	Sampling sites		Data points	
	<i>N</i>	in %	<i>N</i>	in %
6	10 046	33.30	37 699 625	40.87
3	1 689	5.60	25 575 546	27.72
5	6 119	20.29	17 787 408	19.28
2	3 179	10.54	3 226 972	3.50
1	510	1.69	511 697	0.55
7	24	0.08	3 051	0.00
4	2	0.01	687	0.00

Fig. 3. Examples of observed (red) and curated (blue) problems, and final percentage of filled data gaps. A: Example for samples where the wrong country has been assigned in EMPODAT. B: Example for samples located in rivers that represent borders between countries and their coordinates suggest the alternative to the country provided in EMPODAT. C: Example for diverging false country annotations, and missing metadata for the same site. Abbreviations: wbn — water body name, rbn — river basin name, lat — latitude, lon — longitude. D: European map showing EMPODAT samples (all points) from non-marine surface water matrices which could be assigned to seawater (red) based on the provided coordinates. E: Number of values with problems which could be resolved (black) and not resolved (gray) with CleanGeoStreamR stratified by sites and data points; the x-axis evaluates the percentage of the shown numbers for each problem on the y-axis. F: Total number of filled data gaps in the NORMAN Chemical Occurrence Database. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the Helmholtz public GitLab instance and on Bioconda. The package is well-structured and documented. It comes with documented example workflows that can be directly applied to the EMPODAT use case and easily adapted for any other geospatially annotated monitoring database. Additionally, we provide the results of the curation process on Zenodo. See the Data Availability section for details.

4. Discussion

Large-scale environmental monitoring data constitutes one of the most valued resources for data science and predictive approaches in environmental research. The data often originates from multiple projects, laboratories, or institutions that may have focused on or had different rules for their collection. Data collection is usually fieldwork; researchers upload their results and metadata to a database to the best of their knowledge or according to the requirements of their individual projects. Naturally, this introduces various human-made and technical errors, which reduces the usability of such data in large-scale data science studies and AI applications.

As such, we introduce CleanGeoStreamR, a software package that can fill in missing values, resolve inconsistencies, and detect and curate wrong metadata information in environmental (or other) databases that

supply geospatial metadata of sampling sites. We applied it to the NORMAN Chemical Occurrence Database EMPODAT.

Our work on curating and improving the NORMAN Chemical Occurrence Database is unique. While other studies (e.g., Rorije et al. (2022) and Khalidi et al. (2022)) have analyzed the EMPODAT data, ignoring data quality issues, we focused on enhancing data quality by automating the curation of geospatial metadata issues and filling of data gaps. The researchers in Spilsbury et al. (2024) used the EMPODAT data to analyze pharmaceutical contaminants in European waters. They pointed out the importance of comprehensive datasets but did not directly tackle the data curation challenges. In another study that used the same data, missing, incorrect, or non-EU coordinates, samples from international waters and measurements where the country did not match the reported coordinates were dropped (Rorije et al., 2022). This process reduced their dataset from 504 816 to 431 516 by 25 %. In contrast, our study allows us to retain and correct data rather than discard it. For example, we use the ocean shapefile from Natural Earth to detect and correctly classify marine samples, and we apply specialized algorithms to resolve country–coordinate mismatches. This approach enhances the reliability and completeness of the dataset and the amount of re-usable data, which is highly demanded in environmental research.

Additionally, CleanGeoStreamR can be applied to other large-scale environmental datasets such as IPCHEM (European Commission, 2024) and Waterbase (European Environment Agency, 2024), which similarly face challenges related to spatial metadata completeness and accuracy. Our work enhances the utility of the NORMAN dataset for future studies. By addressing these issues at the data preparation stage, it establishes the importance of rigorous data curation in environmental data management.

Spatial metadata curation with the help of CleanGeoStreamR tool led to a significant enhancement regarding the dataset's quality and completeness. Although a successful solution for 36% of the data gaps does not sound impressive, given the scale of the dataset, this outcome represents a significant advancement. In environmental monitoring and spatial analysis, where spatial metadata is often incomplete or inconsistent, having 36% more usable data contributes significantly to added value. This enhanced dataset allows for more comprehensive spatial coverage and more accurate statistical analyses, particularly in large-scale assessments of environmental conditions at the regional, water body, and river basin levels. It must be remembered that even minor improvements in data quality on such datasets could result in significant changes in research findings since every record contributes to a broader understanding of environmental trends. Furthermore, the tool addresses inconsistencies in textual data and coordinates, harmonizing spelling variants and standardizing site information, further improving data coherence. While these inconsistencies cannot be precisely quantified, the improvements fall within a similar range of 35–40%. The effective curation of these metadata ensures that analyses relying on spatial and textual consistency can be conducted more confidently, thereby increasing the dataset's overall utility for environmental and ecological studies.

In summary, CleanGeoStreamR's curation of the spatial metadata, while appearing modest in percentage terms, provides access to a large portion of the dataset that otherwise would have remained inaccessible; therefore, it contributes much to the robustness and reliability of downstream analyses. This improvement represents a major step forward in addressing the challenges of missing, inconsistent, and erroneous data within large-scale environmental datasets, and it will support more accurate and reliable research outcomes in the future. Data reuse strategies are gaining increasing interest in the community; hence, the datasets ready for large-scale analytics, data science, and AI applications will be in high demand.

Many values in the EMPODAT use case data still need to be included. However, there is no automatic way to resolve those since the provided information is insufficient to identify correct water bodies, river basins, or coordinates. For example, there are cases where only a site name in the form of a number and a country is provided, or only country and water body names are there. A solution would be to contact the data-providing institutions and request the missing information, which might mean a tedious task with uncertain success due to the long duration of the data collection and closed projects. Other cases cannot be resolved since the precise spatial information must be confidential.

CleanGeoStreamR can be applied to any future download of the EMPODAT database, integrated into the database's quality management processes, considered in future metadata sheet updates, and adapted for other monitoring databases that face similar problems.

In addition, the CleanGeoStreamR approach offers flexibility for application to other datasets with similar spatial and textual metadata challenges. The tool is designed to be adaptable, allowing users to address missing values, inconsistencies, and errors in a wide variety of environmental or spatial datasets, regardless of the specific geographic region or monitoring focus. This versatility makes CleanGeoStreamR applicable across different domains where the accuracy of spatial metadata is crucial, such as biodiversity monitoring, climate studies, and hydrological research. Our tool reduces the need for manual curation and increases the reproducibility and consistency of data across studies by providing a standardized, automated approach. Furthermore, our work emphasizes the critical role of well-maintained and accurately curated metadata in the broader context of data science and environmental research. Data completeness and consistency directly affect the

validity of subsequent analyses, and the curation of spatial metadata should be prioritized as an essential step in data preparation workflows. By demonstrating the significant improvements achieved through automated curation, we aim to raise awareness about the importance of metadata management in large-scale datasets and encourage greater attention to this often-overlooked aspect of data quality. Properly curated metadata enhances immediate data (re)usability and facilitates future data integration and long-term accessibility, ensuring the value of the collected data is fully realized.

Our solution could impact public health and environmental management by providing high-quality and complete spatial metadata. Considering our collaboration with the NORMAN network and their efforts to overcome the identified problems with geospatial metadata, we are confident that future data points will be of the best possible quality.

5. Conclusion

Handling incomplete, inconsistent, and even wrong spatial metadata presented significant challenges. To address these issues, we cross-referenced known data from other related entries to fill data gaps and resolve inconsistencies and used public external geospatial resources to identify and correct false data. The original data points reveal substantial variability in the presence of crucial metadata, making the automatic curation process complex and challenging. With CleanGeoStreamR, we developed and provided such an automated approach to process vast geospatially annotated metadata of environmental monitoring datasets. The NORMAN Chemical Occurrence Database with its 92 251 604 data points, representing measured chemical concentrations in European surface waters of 30 165 sampling sites, was used to demonstrate CleanGeoStreamR's feasibility. We filled in missing values, resolved inconsistencies, and corrected erroneous records without requiring additional human interaction. The effective and automated spatial metadata curation with CleanGeoStreamR provided a much more valuable dataset. Overall, we successfully achieved the objectives of this paper — to develop an automated tool for curating spatial metadata and to enhance the quality and usability of environmental datasets — through the implementation and demonstration of CleanGeoStreamR. While the tool can be applied to any other dataset with spatial metadata, the processed data can be directly integrated into the original database or reused more confidently in large-scale Big Data analytics or AI applications in environmental and ecological studies. By making the EMPODAT data more reliable and consistent, the dataset is better suited for identifying pollution hotspots, predicting environmental changes, and informing policy decisions. Additionally, the CleanGeoStreamR R package extends these benefits beyond EMPODAT, contributing to improved environmental monitoring practices and supporting future research and policy-making efforts in alignment with FAIR data principles.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

İlhan Mutlu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Data curation. **Jörg Hackermüller:** Conceptualization. **Jana Schor:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

While preparing this manuscript, the authors used Grammarly (Premium license) to check grammar and spelling and to shorten individual paragraphs. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the publication's content.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Software of the CleanGeoStreamR R package is available on GitLab <https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/department-computational-biology/software/cleangeostreamr> and in the Bioconda repository <https://anaconda.org/bioconda/r-cleangeostreamr>. Due to the upload size limit, the used and required input files are uploaded to Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10727168> and the resulting empodat and other related files are uploaded to <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12541868>. Example data can be found in the example folder of the CleanGeoStreamR package’s GitLab repository.

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